

A Study on Knowledge, Attitude and Practices in Patients of Dermatophytosis in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Dermatophytosis is a group of superficial fungal infections that affect the skin, hair, and nails. For the past few years, there has been a rise in the number of cases, along with changing trends in clinical and epidemiological patterns due to inadequate knowledge and practices.

Methods: This is a cross-sectional study of 200 patients with dermatophytosis attending the outpatient department of Dermatology in a tertiary care hospital over a period of 2 months. Basic information of the patient, demographic data, duration of lesions, and careful examination of sites affected, similar lesions in the past were recorded. Questionnaire on knowledge about dermatophytosis, transmission, attitude of patients towards the superficial fungal infection, and practices followed are filled.

Results: A total of 200 patients were recruited in the study. Male to female ratio is 3:2. 57.5% belonged to rural areas and 42.5% urban areas. 52.5% responded that it spreads by touch, 77% and 76% responded that sharing towels, bed sheets, combs, and washing clothes of all family members together increases the chances of infection. 83.5% responded that it spreads from person to person and 98% believed that the disease should be treated. Most of the female respondents (n = 71/80) change sanitary napkins at least twice a day. The majority of the respondents in this study demonstrated practices that perpetuate the spread of fungal infection, such as sharing of clothes, towels, soaps, hats, hairbrushes, combs and wearing tight fitting clothes.

Conclusion: Patients should be educated about personal hygiene, clothing, skin care, corticosteroid abuse, adherence to general measures, and compliance with treatment to ensure a successful outcome.

Keywords: Dermatophytosis, KAP Survey.

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Introduction

Dermatophytosis is a group of superficial fungal infections that affect the skin, hair, and nails with prevalence rate of more than 20-27%. [1] They belong to three different genera, Trichophyton (T), Epidermophyton (E), and Microsporum (M). However, with the advancements in diagnostic tools, three new genera have been identified Nannizzia, Lophophyton, and Arthroderma. [2]

In India, over the past few years, there is an increase in the number of cases along with an epidemiological shift from T. rubrum to T. mentagrophytes/ T. interdigitale. They belong to a particular genotype called T. mentagrophytes Internal transcribed spacer (ITS) Type VIII (now called T. indotineae), which is resistant to the widely used drug terbinafine (TRB). Most

commonly missense mutation has been observed, leading to amino acid substitution, as seen in the squalene epoxide gene with Phe397Leu. [3] There is a rise in the number of atypical presentations, like tinea pseudo-imbricata, tinea incognito (steroid modified tinea), erythrodermic variants of tinea corporis, and an increasing number of patients with tinea faciei. [4] There has been a significant increase in the incidence of dermatophytic infections due to overcrowding, low socio-economic status, inadequate health services, and improper hygiene practices.

Furthermore, aggravating these conditions are sweating and the use of occlusive clothing and footwear. There is an alarming rise in chronic, relapsing, recurrent, nonresponsive, or slowly

responsive cases of superficial dermatophytosis in India that are often unresponsive to conventional drugs and standard doses of recommended antifungal treatment. [5]

There are reports of an increase in the incidence of familial dermatophytosis, most commonly secondary to antifungal resistance, followed by poor adherence to the treatment, topical corticosteroid usage, continued transmission from affected family members, malnutrition, and substandard antifungal drugs. [5]

Aims and objectives:

- To assess the knowledge and attitude of patients about etiology, transmission and preventive options for dermatophytosis.
- To assess practices used in the patient community to manage and prevent dermatophytosis.

Materials and Method:

Study Design: Hospital based cross sectional study (2 months).

Sampling Technique: Convenient sampling.

Sample size and its calculation: Sample size was calculated based on the last 1-year records of tinea patients attending the department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprosy, Gadag Institute of Medical Sciences, Gadag. Total weekly average of 20 cases and total monthly average of 80 cases were recorded. Based on this for 2 months, it will be around 160 tinea patients input. So a sample size of 200 cases attending outpatient department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprosy, Gadag were included.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All the patients presenting with annular scaly lesions with well-defined papulovesicular margin and central clearing.
2. Patients with altered morphology but with positive KOH mount.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients having other concurrent dermatological diseases are excluded.

Collection of samples: Two hundred patients with dermatophytosis attending the OPD of DVL, were

included. After taking written informed consent, a pre-designed and structured close-ended questionnaire with 30 questions was filled. Basic information of the patient, demographic data, duration of lesions, and careful examination of sites affected, similar lesions in the past were recorded. Questionnaire on knowledge about dermatophytosis, transmission, attitude of patients towards the superficial fungal infection, and practices followed were filled. (In case of pediatric patients, details were filled by parents/guardians).

Statistical analysis of the study: The data collected in this study was entered in MS-Excel and analyzed using the statistical software SPSS and the results were calculated in the form of graphs and diagrams. Categorical data was analyzed using Chi-square test. ANOVA test was used. P-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Out of 200 patients, 60% are male and 40% are female. In our study, the age limit ranged from 10 to 70 years with a mean age of 31.93 yrs. Majority of patients are housewives (24%), followed by students (22%), farmers (12%), and drivers (12%). 57.5% belonged to rural areas and 42.5% to urban areas. The most common complaint was itching (58%), followed by discoloration of the skin seen in 19% (Figure 1). The duration of dermatophyte infection was less than 6 months in 74%, between 6 months to 1 year in 21%, and more than 1 year in 5% (Table 1). The most common site is the buttocks and the most common presentation is tinea corporis (Figure 2). 87.5% showed no seasonal variation (Figure 3), while in the remaining 12.5% there was an increase in lesions during the summer. 53% had similar lesions in the past, and 47% have similar complaints in family members. Systemic illnesses like diabetes (9%), hypertension (5.5%), hypothyroidism (3%), cerebral palsy (2%), and HIV on ART (1%) are noted. 26.5% have a habit of tobacco chewing, and 20% consume alcohol. 54% wear tight fitting clothes (Table 2). 63.5% wear synthetic clothes, and 36.5% wear cotton clothing (Figure 4). 59% wear open type footwear, and 41% wear closed type. 28.5% have pets at home or in the vicinity of habitat (Figure 5).

Figure 1: Symptoms

Figure 2: Clinical Presentation

Figure 3: Seasonal Variation

Table 1: Duration of Lesion

Duration	Frequency	Percentage
< 6 months	148	74
1 year	42	21
> 1 year	10	5
Total	200	100

Table 2: Types of Clothes

Types of clothes	Frequency	Percentage
Tight	108	54
Loose	92	46
Total	200	100

Figure 4: Material of Clothes

Figure 5: Pets at Home or in Vicinity of Habitat

Assessment of Knowledge: 50% of patients responded that it is due to fungal infection, and 35% due to allergy. 52.5% responded that it spreads by touch, 37.5% by fomites. Other parameters are assessed in table 3:

Table 3:

Category		Yes	No	Not Sure
Does it spread from one person to person	Frequency	167	20	13
	%	83.5	10	6.5
Does sharing of towels / bed sheets / comb spread it?	Frequency	154	13	33

	%	77	6.5	16.5
Does soaking and washing of clothes of all family members together spread it?	Frequency	152	12	36
	%	76	6	18
Do you know the sites of dermatophytosis occur?	Frequency	157	24	19
	%	78.5	12	9.5
Do you know diabetes / HIV increases risk of dermatophytosis?	Frequency	148	21	31
	%	74	10.5	15.5
Increased humidity at work increases risk of infection?	Frequency	176	5	19
	%	88	2.5	9.5
Can dermatophytosis affect hair?	Frequency	101	22	77
	%	50.5	11	38.5
Can dermatophytosis affect nail?	Frequency	89	26	85
	%	44.5	13	42.5
Are pets a source of infection?	Frequency	90	59	51
	%	45	29.5	25.5
Bathing with hot water decreases infection?	Frequency	163	28	9
	%	81.5	14	4.5

Table 4: Assessment of Attitude

Category		Yes	No	Not Sure
Dermatophytosis is caused due to unhygienic and poor sanitary conditions	Frequency	187	0	13
	%	93.5	0	6.5
Dermatophytosis should be treated	Frequency	196	0	4
	%	98	0	2
All the family members should be treated at once	Frequency	145	15	40
	%	72.5	7.5	20
Dermatophytosis is associated with itching	Frequency	186	10	4
	%	93	5	2
If left untreated it will heal by itself	Frequency	11	169	20
	%	5.5	84.5	10
Washing hands is required after scratching the infections	Frequency	133	32	35
	%	66.5	16	17.5
Washing clothes after every use is necessary	Frequency	140	31	29
	%	70	15.5	14.5
Dermatophytosis is a sexually transmitted infection	Frequency	75	77	48
	%	37.5	38.5	24

Table 5: Assessment Of Practices

Category		No	Yes
Do you rinse clothes after every use?	Frequency	46	154
	%	23	77
Do you soak your clothes in disinfectants / antiseptics?	Frequency	147	53
	%	73.5	26.5
Do you wash and dry feet after working long hours in water logged areas or wearing shoes?	Frequency	98	102
	%	49	51
Do you iron your clothes?	Frequency	167	33
	%	83.5	16.5
Do you use washed towels?	Frequency	39	161
	%	19.5	80.5
Do you share towels / clothes/ soaps?	Frequency	78	122
	%	39	61
Do you wear tight fitting clothes?	Frequency	97	130
	%	48.5	51.5
Do you share your hats/ comb?	Frequency	53	147
	%	26.5	73.5
Did you take any treatment previously	Frequency	103	97
	%	51.5	48.5

History of injectable	Frequency	168	32
	%	84	16
Treatment adherence practices?	Frequency	93	107
	%	46.5	53.5

88.5% bathed at least once a day, and 68.5% dried their clothes in the sun (Figure 6). 51% of patients trim nails once a month, 27% once every 2 months, and 22% once a week.

Most of the female respondents (n = 71/80) change sanitary napkins at least twice a day. 48.5% were treated previously, with 2% treated for less than 1 month, 65% for 1 month to 3 months, 15% for 3 months to 6 months, and 18% for 6 months to at

least a year (Figure 7). Out of which 18.5% were self-treated, 14% of patients applied over the counter medications given by pharmacists, and 6% by dermatologists (Figure 8), duration they applied for is shown in (Table 7). 16% had injectable during their treatment.

15% worsened after treatment, and 16% did not improve on treatment. Only 53.5% showed adherence to treatment.

Figure 6: Practice of Drying the Clothes

Table 6: Over the Counter Topical Cream Application

Topical	Frequency	Percentage
Steroids	19	9.5
Triple combination creams	18	9
Homemade remedies	8	4
Anti-fungal	48	24
Not applied	107	53.5
Total	200	100

Figure 7: Duration of Treatment

Figure 8: Prescribed By

Discussion:

In our study, prevalence in males (60%) is higher than females (40%), which is similar to the Indian study done by Chopra P et al and Ebert A et al. [8,9] As most of the males belong to the working class group, they have highest sweating rate. Lesions are most commonly seen in housewives (24%), and the most common symptom is itching (34.5%), which is in accordance with many Indian studies due to comprehensive attire that traps warmth and moisture which often encourages the growth of fungi. [5] The most common presentation was tinea corporis, followed by tinea cruris, with 74% having lesions for less than 6 months, 16% for at least 1 year, and 10% for more than 1 year, which is similar to the study done by Kumar P et al, Tahiliani S et al and Das S et al. [7,10,11] 53% had similar lesions in the past and 47% had similar complaints in family members, which is supported by a study done by Verma SB et al and Singh BS et al. [5,12] 12.5% have seasonal variation, and frequently seen in summers. 54% of patients wear tight clothes, and 63.5% wear synthetic clothes. 59% use closed footwear. This signifies that increased sweating, occlusive tight clothing, and footwear enhance the chances of acquiring infection. They also lead to friction, causing maceration in areas like the, thighs, lateral aspect of hips, waistband area, and submammary areas. 27% have pets at home or in the vicinity of their habitat. The zoophilic dermatophytes are transferred from animals to humans by hair fragments comprising arthrospores.

52.5% responded that it spreads by touch and 37.5% by fomites, which is similar to the study done by Yamu S et al. [15] The study further revealed knowledge gaps among 16.5% of patients who didn't know that it spreads from one person to other, 23% patients believed that sharing of towels or comb or bed sheets and 24% that washing of clothes of all family members can spread it. The transmission may happen via hair strands and

scales. 57.4% responded correctly by stating that underlying immunosuppression or immunocompromised state increases risk of infection. 55% didn't know infection or spreads from pets.

The attitude regarding superficial fungal infection showed that patients had a strong belief that it is caused due to unhygienic and poor sanitary conditions and should be treated. This positive attitude can be attributed to proper health education on fungal infection. 37.5% believed it is sexually transmitted which is in accordance with the study done by Sivaramakrishnan SA et al. [1] Most of them responded washing hands and clothes after use is required. 10% felt it will heal by itself if left untreated which is worrisome.

In our study 88.5% bathed at least once a day and 68.5% dried their clothes in sun (Figure 6) which is similar to the study by Yamu S et al. [15] moist clothes act as breeding ground for growth of organisms. Majority of the respondents in this study demonstrated practices that perpetuate the spread of fungal infection with the sharing of clothes/ towels/ soaps/ hats/ comb and wearing tight fitting clothes. Most of the chronic cases had recurrence after discontinuing medication which is similar to the study done by AL-Khikani FH et al and Kumar P et al. [7,14] This chronicity of lesions can be attributed secondary to Antifungal resistance, followed by poor adherence to the treatment, over the counter medications like topical Corticosteroids. [11] Reinfection can be due to inadequate source control. Undetected or untreated cases of dermatophytosis have been associated with recurring infections in family members. Due to its infectious nature, fomites are significantly involved in the spread of the disease.

Conclusion

Patients should be educated about personal hygiene, clothing, skin care, corticosteroid abuse, adherence to general measures, and compliance to

treatment to ensure successful outcome. The urgent requirement for accessible and affordable facilities to assess antifungal susceptibility is highlighted in our study. Without such assessments, there is a risk of prolonged treatment, inappropriate drug selection, experimentation with dosages and frequencies, negative impact on the quality of life for patients, and ultimately significant financial losses.

Ethical Approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

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